

The Influence of Gymnastic Training on Human Physical Development

Sabirova Gulchehra Bakhodirovna

Tashkent city, Mirabad district, school 110, 7th grade student, candidate for master of sports

Yorbekova Mavlyuda Ochilovna, Sanakulova Zamira Bakhtiyarjonovna

Sports School specialized in gymnastic sports of Syrdarya region

Annotation: This article analyzes the influence of gymnastics training on human physical development. Gymnastics plays an important role in improving physical strength, flexibility, balance, endurance and coordination. These exercises help not only to strengthen the muscle and bone system, but also to improve the functioning of the cardiovascular system. Gymnastics is recommended as an integral part of a healthy lifestyle for children and adults. The article presents the effects of gymnastics training on physical and mental development, as well as recommendations on how to organize individual training.

Keywords: gymnastics, physical development, flexibility, endurance, balance, physical training, healthy lifestyle.

Enter. Gymnastics is a part of physical education and sports, it is a complex of exercises designed to improve the general physical condition of a person, strengthen the muscular system, normalize the activity of the cardiovascular system and increase flexibility. These classes include various physical exercises and serve to comprehensively develop the body. Gymnastic training is useful not only for athletes, but also for people of different ages and levels of physical fitness.

Today, due to the negative effects of environmental conditions and modern lifestyle, people's physical activity has decreased significantly. Many diseases, in particular, diseases of the cardiovascular system, osteochondrosis, osteoporosis and other diseases of the musculoskeletal system have reduced physical activity and caused the development of these diseases. For this reason, gymnastics training is widespread in order to form a healthy lifestyle, increase physical activity and improve general health.

The main goal of gymnastics training is not only to achieve high results in sports competitions, but also to ensure the proper functioning of various body systems and improve physical development. The importance of physical training and sports activities is great for everyone, regardless of age and physical condition. In particular, gymnastics exercises play an important role in increasing the elasticity of muscles, strengthening the strength of bones, and ensuring the effective functioning of the cardiovascular system.

In addition to improving physical condition, gymnastics also has psychological benefits. They serve to reduce stress, improve mental health and encourage a person to lead an active lifestyle. Therefore, gymnastics is a necessary tool not only for physical development, but also for the formation of a general healthy lifestyle.

The article talks about the effect of gymnastics training on human physical development, its benefits to various systems, in particular, muscles, bones and cardiovascular system, as well as the effective organization of training.

Material and method. A methodological approach was used to study the effects of gymnastics training, based on the results of literature analysis, scientific research and practical training. We focused on showing and analyzing how the systems of the human body adapt to gymnastics training and improve physical condition. For this purpose, the intensity, periodicity, and effectiveness of training were studied.

Results. The main benefits of gymnastics training were observed in the following areas:

1. **Muscular system and bones** : Gymnastics activates all muscle groups of the body, which helps to increase strength and endurance . These exercises have a positive effect on bone strengthening, bone mass and their development.
2. **Cardiovascular system** : Gymnastics helps to strengthen the cardiovascular system. It helps the system work efficiently, normalizes blood circulation and heart rate.
3. **Flexibility and balance** : Gymnastics training improves flexibility and balance of movements. These words, in particular, help to increase the flexibility needed to overcome traction and challenges.
4. **Physical and mental health** : Exercise can help reduce stress and improve physical and mental health. By increasing their physical activity, motivation and productivity can be increased.

Discussion. The influence of gymnastics training on human physical development is extensive, it makes changes in the muscular system, bones and cardiovascular system. At the same time, gymnastics can lead to injuries if it is not controlled and performed incorrectly. Therefore, it is necessary to organize training with an individual approach, taking into account the physical condition. It should be noted that gymnastics is useful not only for young people and athletes, but also for people of any age. This is especially important for people who have physical limitations or spend a lot of time in front of a computer.

Summary. Gymnastics training is an indispensable tool for improving human physical development and forming a healthy lifestyle. It ensures efficient functioning of the muscular system, bones and cardiovascular system and improves general physical condition. Organizing classes with an individual approach is also a necessary tool to avoid injuries and maintain a healthy lifestyle.

Used literature

1. Shutova T. N., Gadzhiev D. M., Pikhayev R. R. Conceptual elementary athletic gymnastics and physical education of students //physical culture, sport, tourism: scientific and methodological support. - 2016. - S. 134-138.
2. Kiuchukov I. et al. Impact of gymnastics training on the health-related physical fitness of young female and male artistic gymnasts //Science of Gymnastics Journal. - 2019. - T. 11. – no. 2. - S. 175-187.
3. Rustamova C. R., Yakubova M. M. Optimization diagnostic errors in the amyotrophic lateral sclerosis //International journal of conference series on education and social sciences (Online). – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 3.
4. Yakubova M. M. et al. Clinical and neurological aspects of multiple sclerosis during infection with covid-19 in uzbekistan //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2021. – T. 2. – №. 3. – C. 186-190.
5. Yakubova M. M. et al. Metabolites Of The Gut Microbiota Support Cognitive Function By Increasing The Production Of Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor BDNF //Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results. – 2023. – C. 7626-7634.
6. Yakubova M. Disturbed gut microbiota leads to cognitive impairment. – 2023.
7. Якубова М. М. The study of the causes and stress dependence of hand tremor in military. – 2023.
8. Якубова М. М. Characteristics of cognitive function in type 2 diabetes. – 2023.
9. Yakubova, Marhamat. "Changes in Melatonin Concentration Depending on the Severity of Chronic Cerebral Ischemia and Seasonality." (2023).
10. Rudd JR et al. The impact of gymnastics on children's physical self-concept and movement skill development in primary schools //Measurement in physical education and exercise science. - 2017.

- T. 21. – no. 2. - S. 92-100.

11. Kiuchukov I. et al. Impact of gymnastics training on the health-related physical fitness of young female and male artistic gymnasts //Science of Gymnastics Journal. - 2019. - T. 11. – no. 2. - S. 175-187.
12. Gurd B., Klentrow P. Physical and pubertal development in young male gymnasts //Journal of Applied Physiology. - 2003. - T. 95. – no. 3. - S. 1011-1015.